

The Better Man: A Feministic View

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Anita Nair is one of the eminent women novelists in contemporary India; she has earned honors for her originality, propensity and for her societal dedication. She presents women characters in her novels with full of enormous courage. As an Indian woman and the experiences of women around her she perfectly understood the societal-cultural problems of women. The celebrated author was born at Kundakottakurissi, near Shornur in Kerala. Her works of fiction have been translated into 21 languages. She studied in Chennai before moving back Kerala, where she obtained a BA in English Literature. She worked as the creative director of an advertising agency in Bangalore. It was at this time in 1977 that she wrote her first book, a collection of short stories titled *Satyr of the Subway*. In fact, the book earned her appreciation and she also won her a fellowship from the Virginia Center for Creative Arts. She has made a debut in children's literature also. Nair has also written *The Puffin Book of Myths and Legends* (2004), a children's book on myths and legends. Nair has also edited *Where the Rain is Born* (2003). Nair's writings about Kerala and her poetry has been included in *The Poetry India Collection* and *British Council Poetry Workshop Anthology*. Her poems appeared in many prestigious poetry anthologies like *The Dance of the Peacock: An Anthology of English Poetry from India*, featuring 151 Indian English poets, edited by Vivekanand Jha and published by Hidden Brook Press, Canada. It is interesting to note that *The Better Man* is a novel by Anita Nair. It is set in the northern part of Kerala, India, a region known as Malabar under the British Raj. The Better Man is set in contemporary India in a little fictitious village called Kaikurussi in the northern part of Kerala. This region was once known as Malabar during the British regime. After Independence, Malabar as a geographical region ceased to exist. Though Malabar has no presence on a map of India, it still exists as a state of mind: laid-back, slow, to live and let live. So much so, the northern Malabarists treat the enterprising and hard-working southerners with a disdain bordering on contempt. A person from Malabar is so entrenched in the past that thinking of the morrow is almost impossible. And yet, there is a discontent that is almost palpable. Perhaps this is the reason why the region that was once Malabar saw the growth of

Naxalites [extremists who combined Marxism with violence against all organized systems]; still has the highest recorded number of lunatics and suicides in India and has fundamentalist political groups thriving side by side with communist strongholds.

Notably, Kaikurussi the village is in a little hollow surrounded by several hills. It has nothing there that would make any one come looking for it. It is neither the birthplace of a Mahatma nor a movement. No miracles have ever happened there. In fact, nothing of significance ever happens there to anyone. In fact, there is not even a road running through Kaikurussi or a river flowing alongside it. All Kaikurussi has to define its topography are fields, wells, a mountain and distant hills. An elderly bachelor and a retired government employee, Mukundan is forced by circumstances to return to Kaikurussi, the village he was born in. A village that he fled when he was eighteen. And now back in his ancestral house, he finds himself unable to cope. He is haunted by a sense of failure. For having abandoned his mother. For not measuring up to his still alive and domineering father Achuthan Nair's expectations. For having gone through life without really living it. And then there is the village itself. Mukundan realizes that he has no role to play in the village. In fact, he discovers that what should have been his rightful place had been usurped by an upstart Power House Ramakrishnan. In the first few weeks of his exile, he meets up with a wayward genius. Bhasi or One-screw-loose -Bhasi as he is known is a house painter and a practitioner of a mongrel system of medicine, he has evolved by combining several kinds of healing processes - herbal cures, principles of Homeopathy.... Bhasi is deeply disturbed by Mukundan's anguish and decides to mend the cracks in Mukundan's much battered psyche. He cajoles, manipulates and shapes Mukundan's transformation. But the superficiality of the change is revealed soon. Power House Ramakrishnan on a cruel whim decides to build a community hall in the village. And chooses Bhasi's piece of land as the site to build on. When Bhasi refuses to sell his land, Power House Ramakrishnan threatens to break his business and run him out of the village. As the richest and most powerful man of the village Power House Ramakrishnan was capable of doing just that and